

Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics Revisited: A Mathematical Assessment of the Ontological Aspects

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Abstract: The ontological aspects of the Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics are studied within a mathematical framework. It is demonstrated that parallel worlds adhering to a deterministic interpretation of quantum mechanics are statistically unlikely to persist in the long-term ontology of the MWI. This means that the parallel worlds whose sentient beings approve a deterministic substance for quantum mechanics statistically must become extinct in classical limits.

Keywords: Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics, Long-Term Ontology, Classical Limits, Determinism, Deterministic Law, Uncertainty Principle, Parallel Worlds, Statistical History, Predictive Analytics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The many-worlds interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics has received widespread attention in recent decades.¹ However, as we will explain in the following, this interpretation has a long way to go to become a reliable scientific theory with a consistent epistemological and ontological background.² The most well-known flaw of the MWI is its untestability. As a physical theory, falsifiability through experimental evidence must be the most necessary property of the MWI. However, testing the validity of the MWI is, in fact, out of our present and foreseeing experimental capabilities.³ In addition, the MWI has faced several intellectual/theoretical criticisms including philosophical objections based on the law of Occam's razor principle,⁴ the probability problem and the credibility of the Born rule in the interpretation,⁵ the trouble of the ambiguity of the preferred basis,⁶ and its incompleteness as an alternative interpretation for the measurement postulate of quantum mechanics.⁷

In fact, besides several objections to its empirical and theoretical aspects, such an interpretation seems to suffer from an inherently contradictory nature in its underlying ontological viewpoint.⁸ However, it must be emphasized that the entire mentioned objections of the MWI, probably except the

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¹ See for example [9, 12, 16–18, 21, 49, 64] and the references therein.

² The reliability of the MWI is still a controversial topic. For more details see the discussions in [1, 3, 5–10, 14, 15, 19, 20, 23–25, 27, 28, 34, 35, 37, 39–44, 50–52, 55, 56, 60, 63, 66, 67, 71].

³ See for example [9, 14, 26, 42].

⁴ For more discussion see [33, 45, 70] and the references therein.

⁵ See [23, 42–44, 46, 67].

⁶ See for example [22, 39, 42, 68].

⁷ See [37, 41] for more discussions.

⁸ Actually, controversial claims have been raised in defending or criticizing this interpretation. See for example [2–4, 7, 9, 11, 13, 14, 24, 27, 29, 32, 42, 48, 49, 53, 54, 57, 61, 65, 69].

testability, stem inherently from the explanations of the interpretation in classical limits, or equivalently, from the long-term aspects of its ontology.⁹ These contradictions and their various aspects have been examined in several ways and it has been shown that the MWI will result in theoretical/empirical shortcomings when we approach the classical perspectives.¹⁰

One of the most important flaws of the long-term ontological aspects of the MWI is related to the existence of parallel worlds whose sentient beings experience a deterministic law in quantum measurements, such as a periodic rule for observations or observing the same outcomes in all the measurements. Obviously, such parallel observers disapprove of the whole or some parts of quantum mechanics, and hence, adopt a different understanding of physical reality. In other words, the MWI inevitably results in the appearance of some parallel observers who experimentally, within classical viewpoints, refute at least some pivotal portions of the MWI itself. In principle, a significant part of the criticisms of the MWI is rooted in such classical expectations/explanations of the ontological aspects of the interpretation.

Actually, as we will show in this paper, the classical limits of the MWI's ontology lead to the emergence of observers who disapprove of the inherent uncertainty of quantum mechanics as an empirical law of physics. Such observers, as mentioned above, experience a deterministic law in some parts of quantum measurements. Although these parallel worlds are rarely created they really exist in the ontology of the MWI, and this existence, as we will show delicately, is the main source of a theoretical contradiction in the classical pictures of the interpretation. In principle, the inconsistency arises because observers who adhere to a definite rule for outcomes and reject the MWI may diverge from those who accept MWI at such a late stage in the interpretation's long-term ontology that they become experimentally indistinguishable from one another.

In fact, we will show that the ontological nature of the MWI leads to two contradictory following theoretical/empirical facts:

Fact 1) The validity of the MWI and its ontological features in classical limits will lead to the confirmation of the indeterministic nature of quantum mechanics in some but not all parallel worlds.¹¹

Fact 2) The indeterministic essence of quantum mechanics has a statistical nature that can be refuted or confirmed only by examining the long-term statistical history of laboratory observations.

Essentially, as we aim to demonstrate, these theoretical/empirical facts represent two contradictory propositions. This conclusion reveals the inherent contradictions in the MWI of quantum mechanics at classical limits.¹² We will try to illustrate this problem with a concrete mathematical approach; We will first introduce a real-valued function f that assigns each parallel world a value in $[0, 1]$

⁹ For more details about the ontological viewpoint of the MWI see [7, 32, 65, 66]. The main ontological viewpoint of Everett's interpretation could be found in [31] and also in DeWitt's work [30].

¹⁰ See for example [1, 8, 9, 20, 35, 42–44, 66].

¹¹ We are aware that the MWI actually rejects the measurement postulate of quantum mechanics and, hence Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. But, here only the validity of the inherent uncertainty of quantum mechanics is examined from the viewpoints of the sentient beings of the parallel worlds.

¹² In fact, in this paper, our focus is only on the long-term aspects of the MWI's ontology, while we assume that the interpretation may be valid and consistent at quantum levels.

that represents its sentient being's scientific assessment regarding the rate of validity of the inherent uncertainty in quantum mechanics. Then after, we will challenge the long-term ontology of Everett's interpretation directly by addressing the two facts, **Fact 1** and **Fact 2**, via the topological features of f . It is seen that the definition of f indicates that the classical picture of the MWI confronts the with a mathematical contradiction.

By employing the above strategy we will prove that the very understanding of the classical ontology of the MWI is inherently contradictory. However, the good news is that this issue can be resolved by restricting the MWI to below classical limits and to short-term processes where no statistical information is derived from observations. An alternative and more sophisticated approach is to limit the long-term framework of the MWI to those parallel worlds in which sentient beings experimentally validate the physical laws of quantum mechanics, excluding those that do not. This entails assuming an extinction process within MWI, where parallel worlds that fail to align with the prevailing understanding of quantum physics gradually disappear.

II. INDETERMINISM OF QUANTUM MECHANICS AND THE MWI

Let us temporarily assume that the complete set of quantum measurements is provided by a single experiment with two possibilities, such as measuring the electron spin in some specific direction. The measurements take place over a large enough ensemble comprising of \mathcal{N} ($\mathcal{N} \gg 1$) copies of a single quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ which is the eigenstate of an operator that does not commute with the measurement operator. For theoretical reasons, we will assume $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$, where $|\alpha|^2 = |\beta|^2 = \frac{1}{2}$, while $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are the two eigenstates of the measurement.

Suppose the observation could be performed any number of times n , as long as it is feasible. Based on the ontology of the MWI, any parallel world created after n measurements is uniquely determined by a binary sequence of n digits in $\{0, 1\}$. We denote this sequence as $S = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$, where $a_i = 0$ (or $a_i = 1$) indicates observing a 0 (or 1) at the i -th measurement. In other words, after n measurements, all the created parallel worlds are characterized by the set of all binary sequences with n elements.

Now, assume that after n observations, the agents assign a real value in $I = [0, 1]$ that indicates the probability of the truth of the uncertainty of quantum mechanics, or equivalently the indeterminism of the theory. These numbers can be represented via a piecewise constant function, say $f_n : [0, 1) \rightarrow I$, so that if an agent records observations $S = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ and obtains p_n for their supposed assessment, then we define¹³

$$f_n(x) = p_n \quad \text{for any } x \in [0.a_1 \dots a_n, 0.a_1 \dots (a_n + 1)), \quad (\text{II.1})$$

wherein it is assumed that if $a_n = 1$ then

$$0.a_1 \dots a_{n-1}(a_n + 1) = 0.a_1 \dots (a_{n-1} + 1)0 \quad (\text{II.2})$$

and vice versa.¹⁴ We should note that here the number $0.a_1 \dots a_n$, the so-called the *world's code*, is

¹³ We can compare this idea with what is studied in [36]. Also, see [62] and [54] for more useful discussions.

¹⁴ Note that in this paper, we use the standard notation where $0.a_1 \dots a_n$ represents $0.a_1 \dots a_n 000 \dots$ whose digits are followed by an infinite sequence of zeros.

assumed in base 2, and hence, we have

$$\bigcup_{a_1, \dots, a_n \in \{0,1\}} [0.a_1 \dots a_n, 0.a_1 \dots (a_n + 1)) = [0, 1). \quad (\text{II.3})$$

The function $f_n : [0, 1) \rightarrow I$ is referred to as the *assessment function*.¹⁵ For theoretical reasons, we are interested in studying the analytic properties of f_n via experimental methods and estimate its discontinuity gaps. To do this, note that the discontinuity points of f_n can be classified into two sets: **1)** The discontinuities occurring at points with $a_n = 0$, and **2)** The discontinuities appearing at points where $a_n = 1$.

It is easily seen that for discontinuities occurring at points with $a_n = 0$, each pair of adjacent intervals $I_1 = [0.a_1 \dots a_{n-1}0, 0.a_1 \dots a_{n-1}1)$ and $I_2 = [0.a_1 \dots a_{n-1}1, 0.a_1 \dots (a_{n-1} + 1)0)$ represent two observational histories that differ only at the last outcome, i.e., $\{a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, 0\}$ and $\{a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, 1\}$. Hence, in this case, for any $x \in I_1$ and $y \in I_2$ we logically expect that:

$$|f_n(x) - f_n(y)| \propto 1/n. \quad (\text{II.4})$$

However, for the case of discontinuities appearing at points where $a_n = 1$, we are faced with more difficult situations. In this case, the two adjacent intervals $I_1 = [0.a_1 \dots a_{n-1}1, 0.a_1 \dots (a_{n-1} + 1)0)$ and $I_2 = [0.a_1 \dots (a_{n-1} + 1)0, 0.a_1 \dots (a_{n-1} + 1)1)$ depict two statistical records that differ at least in the last two observations, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} a_{n-1} = 0 & \Rightarrow S_1 = \{a_1, \dots, a_{n-2}, 0, 1\} & \text{and} & S_2 = \{a_1, \dots, a_{n-2}, 1, 0\} \\ a_{n-1} = 1, a_{n-2} = 0 & \Rightarrow S_1 = \{a_1, \dots, a_{n-3}, 0, 1, 1\} & \text{and} & S_2 = \{a_1, \dots, a_{n-3}, 1, 0, 0\} \\ a_{n-1} = a_{n-2} = 1, a_{n-3} = 0 & \Rightarrow S_1 = \{a_1, \dots, a_{n-4}, 0, 1, 1, 1\} & \text{and} & S_2 = \{a_1, \dots, a_{n-4}, 1, 0, 0, 0\} \\ & \vdots & & \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II.5})$$

Consequently, evaluating $|f_n(x) - f_n(y)|$ ($x \in I_1$ and $y \in I_2$) is more complicated in this case. To analyze this subtlety one should reconsider the essence of the uncertainty principle with more delicacy.

One should note that since $|\psi\rangle$ is the eigenstate of an operator that does not commute with the measurement operator, verifying the uncertainty principle's viability makes no sense practically. Since, if $|\psi\rangle$ is an eigenstate of the x -spin operator S_x (e.g. $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|+\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|-\rangle$) and the measurements are conducted by operating z -spin operator S_z , then it would be obvious that $\Delta S_x = \langle S_y \rangle = 0$ which automatically satisfies the uncertainty principle $\Delta S_x \Delta S_z \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} |\langle S_y \rangle|$, regardless to the amount of the variance of the statistics of the agent's observations ΔS_z ; All agents approve the main formula of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle $\Delta A \Delta B \geq \frac{1}{2} |\langle [A, B] \rangle|$ statistically.

Nevertheless, although the uncertainty principle is allegedly satisfied in any circumstances, the inherent uncertainty of the theory, or equivalently the indeterminism of quantum mechanics may be violated in some parallel worlds. For instance, if an agent records a long enough history of "seesaw"

¹⁵ For an experiment with $p + 1$ possible outcomes, the sequences of parallel worlds consist of numbers in $\{0, \dots, p\}$, and the world's code is an element of $[0, 1)$ in base $p + 1$. This coding process can be easily extended to k different types of experiments. In this case, the created parallel worlds are coded with elements of $[0, 1)^k$. In this situation, any parallel world is identified with k sequences, each of which determines a specific number in $[0, 1)$ in the base of some appropriate number.

observations, i.e. $S = \{1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, \dots\}$, despite validating Heisenberg's uncertainty formula, they may adopt a deterministic understanding of quantum mechanics that contradicts the fundamental nature of uncertainty. More precisely, there is a subtle difference between Heisenberg's uncertainty formula and the broader concept of uncertainty in quantum mechanics. The former can be satisfied while the latter is violated. That is, Heisenberg's uncertainty formula could still hold in a deterministic interpretation of the theory, such as the MWI.

Thus, the assessment of the essence of the uncertainty of quantum mechanics should be conducted based on the statistical order of the observations and the power of predictability of the next outcomes. This is the main focus of *predictive analytics*. Predictive analytics is, by definition, the practice of using data, statistical algorithms, and machine learning techniques to identify the likelihood of future outcomes based on historical data. It is commonly applied to forecast potential scenarios and aid in decision-making across various fields of science and social activities. By analyzing patterns and trends in past data, predictive analytics helps us anticipate future events, predict more probable expectations, and make more informed decisions [59].

Essentially, finding fundamental patterns and predictive formulas in historical data is one of the most complex scientific processes, often requiring machine learning and artificial intelligence, and in highly complex cases, quantum computers. However, in this article, we will examine the simplest predictive formulas that are identified by *short recurring patterns* in the historical data of recorded results. This simplification of quantum mechanical uncertainty means that, from our perspective, the history of observations in quantum experiments does not follow any short recurring pattern. We should clarify that the term "short" in "short recurring patterns" refers to the requirement that the pattern can be identified with current quantum laboratory techniques. It should not necessitate years of continuous repetition of a quantum experiment to be discovered. For example, if an agent records n zeros out of n measurements, they might be inclined to consider the uncertainty of quantum mechanics a false proposition, especially when n is sufficiently large.

Based on the contents of (II.5), the statistical order of the last outcomes of the recorded observations in each row is fixed because it results from a simple exchange of $1 \leftrightarrow 0$. In this regard, the different observational records are

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{n-1} = 0 & \Rightarrow |S_1 - S_2| = \{0, \dots, 0, 1, 1\} \\
 a_{n-1} = 1, a_{n-2} = 0 & \Rightarrow |S_1 - S_2| = \{0, \dots, 0, 1, 1, 1\} \\
 a_{n-1} = a_{n-2} = 1, a_{n-3} = 0 & \Rightarrow |S_1 - S_2| = \{0, \dots, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1\} \\
 & \vdots
 \end{aligned} \tag{II.6}$$

wherein 1 represents a sign of difference, while 0 indicates agreement.

Indeed, in (II.6), the number of 1s is equal to the number of consecutive 0s at the end of the lower bound of I_2 plus one. Let us denote this number by n_0 . Therefore, if $n_0 \ll n$, transferring from I_1 to I_2 results in a few perturbations in the statistics of observations, producing a variation of order $1/n$ in the value of the assessment function f_n . Hence, since we only consider the short recurring patterns, for small n_0 but significantly large n , the effect of movement from I_1 to I_2 is definitely detectable as a shift between outcomes 1 and 0, provided a pattern has been effectively recognized. Otherwise, if no short pattern has been detected in this case, the flip of the last few outcomes will not produce a recurring pattern.

On the other hand, since observations become more and more critical for scientific inferences as the experiments are increasing, if both n and n_0 are practically large, swapping $1 \leftrightarrow 0$ in the final observed zeros does not affect assessment about the predicability of the next outcome regardless of the ratio n_0/n , provided we only concentrate on the short recurring patterns within the recorded outcomes. In other words, as n and n_0 increase significantly, the observational histories related to I_1 and I_2 have effectively the same impacts on the predictive power of the agents, and hence, the value of f_n is practically conserved along the transfer from I_1 to I_2 .

Consequently, based on (II.4) and the above arguments we conclude that for large n , if $|x-y| < 1/2^n$, then $|f_n(x) - f_n(y)| < C/n$ regardless of the kind the included discontinuities. Here, C represents an arbitrary constant that depends on the maximum length of the short recurring patterns we considered. All in all, we have:

$$|x - y| < \frac{1}{2^n} \quad \Rightarrow \quad |f_n(x) - f_n(y)| < \frac{C}{\log_2 |x - y|}. \quad (\text{II.7})$$

However, the property (II.7) can be rewritten via some more general formulation. Indeed, we can assume that for large enough n the following statement holds:

$$|x - y| < \frac{1}{2^n} \quad \Rightarrow \quad |f_n(x) - f_n(y)| < \rho(|x - y|), \quad (\text{II.8})$$

where $\rho(x) : [0, 1) \rightarrow I$ is a continuous function. In the following, we use (II.8) as the analytic property of assessment functions f_n s.

Now, let us define the *final assessment function* $f : [0, 1) \rightarrow I$ as

$$f(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x), \quad x \in [0, 1). \quad (\text{II.9})$$

From the perspective of empiricism/experimentalism, the process $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x)$ must converge.¹⁶ In fact, this convergence implies that observers can make stable and confident scientific inferences based on progressively more data. Hence, by definition, for each $x \in [0, 1)$ and any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists some N so that for all $n \geq N$, we have $|f(x) - f_n(x)| < \varepsilon$. Furthermore, because the number of experiments is practically finite (i.e., \mathcal{N}), there exists a sufficiently large \mathcal{N} such that $f_{\mathcal{N}}(x)$ and $f(x)$ are practically equal for all $x \in [0, 1)$. This property is referred to as *finite convergence property*.

Essentially, the finite convergence property is considered from an empirical perspective, implying that scientific conclusions should reach definite results within a finite period based on experimental history. However, this property needs to be carefully defined to align smoothly with other foundational assumptions. Thus, we assume that it works like the uniform convergence property. That is, we suppose that for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists an N such that for all $n \geq N$ and any $x \in [0, x)$, it holds that $|f(x) - f_n(x)| < \varepsilon$. The following theorem provides significant information about f .

Theorem 1; *The final assessment function $f : [0, 1) \rightarrow I$ is continuous.*

Proof; Assume that $\varepsilon > 0$ is given. Based on the finite convergence property there exists an N_1 such that for all $n \geq N_1$ and any $x \in [0, x)$, it holds that $|f(x) - f_n(x)| < \varepsilon/3$. Let N_2 be the large

¹⁶ Although the definition of f involves an idealization in taking the number of observations to infinity, its basis of empiricism ensures that it should be considered a practical result of the basic assumptions of the MWI.

enough integer that if $|x - y| < 2^{-N_2}$, then $\rho(|x - y|) < \varepsilon/3$. For example, for $\rho(x) = -1/\log_2(x)$, we have $N_2 = \lceil 3/\varepsilon \rceil + 1$. Now, define $N = \text{Max}\{N_1, N_2\}$. Based on (II.8), if $|x - y| < 2^{-N}$, then $|f_N(x) - f_N(y)| < \varepsilon/3$. Therefore, we readily obtain

$$|f(x) - f(y)| \leq |f(x) - f_N(x)| + |f_N(x) - f_N(y)| + |f(y) - f_N(y)| < \varepsilon, \quad (\text{II.10})$$

for all $x, y \in [0, 1)$ with $|x - y| < 2^{-N}$. This finishes the theorem. **Q.E.D.**

The result of **Theorem 1** is entirely rational because the closer two numbers in the interval $[0, 1)$ are to each other, the longer their initial digit sequences are similar. This means that their agents have recorded more similar histories in their observations, and thus their understanding of quantum mechanics is more alike. Therefore, as we see, the ontological premise of the MWI puts a natural topology on the space of the parallel worlds induced from $[0, 1)$. Indeed, **Theorem 1** shows that this topology has an intimate correlation with the statistical/empirical nature of the uncertainty of quantum mechanics; The closer the two world's codes are to each other, the more similar understanding of uncertainty of quantum mechanics their sentient beings have. Therefore, the induced topology on the set of all parallel worlds substantially reflects the rate of validity of indeterminism from the perspective of the agents of the created parallel worlds.¹⁷

Let us have a closer overview of the ontology of the parallel worlds created by the assumed experiments. According to the very assumptions of the MWI, any possible parallel world has an equal likelihood to emerge in the ontology. Let $x_1, x_2 \in [0, 1)$ be two real numbers in base 2 that represent parallel worlds ω_1 and ω_2 , whose agents record the following history of observations, respectively;

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\omega_1} &= \{a_1, \dots, a_{N_0}, b_1, \dots, b_m, b_1, \dots, b_m, b_1, \dots, b_m, \dots\}, \\ S_{\omega_2} &= \{a_1, \dots, a_{N_0}, c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II.11})$$

where in N_0 is arbitrary but practically possible for a sequence of observations, $m \geq 1$ is not too big to be able to provide a short recurring pattern with $b_1, \dots, b_m \in \{0, 1\}$, and $\{c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots\}$ is a truly random sequence of digits in $\{0, 1\}$ including no short recurring patterns. Indeed, we have¹⁸

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= 0.a_1 \dots a_{N_0} b_1 \dots b_m b_1 \dots b_m b_1 \dots b_m \dots, \\ x_2 &= 0.a_1 \dots a_{N_0} c_1 c_2 c_3 \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II.12})$$

We emphasize that it is not supposed that the number of digits of x_1 and x_2 is endless; instead, they are practically assumed to be sufficiently large so that the agents of ω_1 and ω_2 are able to infer definite scientific conclusions about the proposed indeterminism of quantum mechanics. Consequently, if ω_1

¹⁷ We should note that this argument applies to numbers without an infinite terminal sequence of 1s. This consideration is practically reasonable since almost all of the numbers in $[0, 1)$ fall into this category, and the set of the numbers with sequences terminating in infinite 1s has Lebesgue measure zero. However, in such rare parallel worlds, observers will conclude that quantum mechanics has a deterministic nature.

¹⁸ Effectively, we have assumed that x_1 is a truncation of a rational number. In other words, a famous theorem in number theory states that a real number $0 \leq r < 1$ is rational if and only if

$$r = 0.a_1 \dots a_m b_1 \dots b_n b_1 \dots b_n b_1 \dots b_n \dots,$$

for some $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, wherein a_i s and b_j s belong to $\{0, \dots, p - 1\}$ whenever r is assumed in base p . See [38] for more details.

can survive in the long-term ontology of the MWI, its agent would definitely conclude that quantum mechanics is a deterministic theory. Hence, experimentally we must have $f(x_1) = 0$. On the other hand, if ω_2 is sustainable in the classical limits of the MWI, its agent must discover an indeterministic essence for quantum mechanics, leading to the experimental conclusion $f(x_2) = 1$.

We must emphasize that the conclusions $f(x_1) = 0$ and $f(x_2) = 1$ are derived from experimental considerations and are not directly related to the formal mathematical definition of the final assessment function f . These conclusions follow from the hypothetical existence of parallel worlds ω_1 and ω_2 within the long-term ontology of the MWI. But the crucial question is whether both worlds ω_1 and ω_2 can be created within the ontology of the MWI. In other words, does the structural framework of the MWI have the capacity to encompass both worlds? The following theorem answers these questions by showing that ω_1 and ω_2 cannot both persist along the long-term ontology of the MWI and at least one of them must become extinct in classical limits.

Theorem 2; *The assumptions $f(x_1) = 0$ and $f(x_2) = 1$ are experimentally contradictory.*

Proof; Set $\varepsilon = 1$. Since f is continuous there exists some N_0 such that for each $x_1, x_2 \in [0, 1]$ with $|x_1 - x_2| < 2^{-N_0}$, we have $|f(x_1) - f(x_2)| < 1$. This is in contradiction with the experimental hypothesis of the theorem, provided N_0 in (II.11) is large enough. However, by assumptions, we must ensure that N_0 is practically feasible and much smaller than the total number of experiments \mathcal{N} . In fact, it appears that N_0 meets these criteria since $\varepsilon = 1$ is the supremum variation of f , i.e., $\text{Sup}_{x,y \in (0,1]} |f(x) - f(y)| = 1$, and hence, we naturally expect that $|f(x_1) - f(x_2)| < 1$ is easily satisfied without having to go to the trouble of finding x_1 and x_2 sufficiently close to each other. Consequently, we naturally have $N_0 \ll \mathcal{N}$. This finishes the theorem. **Q.E.D.**

In fact, the inconsistency that was pointed out in **Theorem 2**, stems from the naive generalization of the main consequences of the MWI to long-term processes. Strictly speaking, acknowledging the MWI of quantum mechanics in classical limits contradicts the indeterministic nature of the theory. In other words, if the parallel worlds do not exist objectively at classical limits, then f , with its properties, cannot be defined based on empirical concepts. More precisely, the assumption of the existence and definability of the assessment functions f_{ns} for large enough ns is the paradoxical core that was addressed in **Theorem 2**. Consequently, we conclude that the very understanding of the MWI is inauthentic for long-term processes and some parallel worlds must become extinct in the classical limits.

Substantially, the main reason for the contradictory nature of the long-term ontology of the MWI stems from including the semi-deterministic parallel worlds where the uncertain nature of quantum mechanics is rejected thoroughly by the measurement outcomes.¹⁹ Indeed, the uncontrolled creation of parallel worlds in the long-term ontology of the MWI will produce some fatal defects, such as the existence of semi-deterministic worlds that refute some pivotal parts of quantum mechanics and collapse the mathematical structure of the interpretation. More precisely, the semi-deterministic observers who

¹⁹ We use the prefix "semi" for these parallel worlds for caution because quantum physics is absolutely valid in all unmeasured physical events in the natures of these parallel worlds.

are the inevitable results of the long-term ontology of the MWI disapprove of quantum mechanics, and hence, the MWI itself. Consequently, this paradoxical loop breaks down the mathematical and experimental consistency of the interpretation.

At the beginning of this section, when we introduced the model studied in this paper and its experiment, we used the term "temporary" for the proposed hypotheses. It is now time to retract the term "temporary" and demonstrate that the model examined in this paper is applicable to more serious issues in MWI. A common understanding of the MWI is that the process of generating parallel worlds is linked to all quantum phenomena occurring in the universe. From this perspective, the method presented above might be criticized because we only examined observations related to experiments conducted by designated agents. However, it should be noted that such a limitation never undermines our study. In fact, we must emphasize that each parallel world in our studies effectively represents an equivalence class of all the parallel worlds generated in the MWI that agree on the outcomes of the experiments we examined, regardless of the difference in other quantum mechanical events outside the laboratory or irrelevant to the measurements.

With such precision in analyzing and generalizing the concept of parallel worlds to the aforementioned equivalence classes, there is no doubt that the study method presented in this article and its results will rigorously challenge the intellectual foundation of the MWI in classical limits. This indicates that any explanation of the MWI must confront the paradox introduced in this paper and must address its resolution. However, we must emphasize that our results in this paper cannot assess the validity or invalidity of MWI within quantum limits. In fact, evaluating the accuracy of this interpretation for short-term processes is beyond the scope of our methodological approach. Our calculations only indicate that if we wish to extend the interpretation to classical limits, serious ontological considerations must be applied and some exotic parallel worlds must be excluded from the perspective of the MWI.

In other words, classical narratives of the MWI such as the existence of multiple copies of "I" in other parallel worlds with different physics theories, are inherently flawed even if the interpretation is genuinely correct. Perhaps, a useful explanation of the conclusion of **Theorem 2** is that parallel worlds behave like off-shell particles in quantum field theory and the Standard Model; They violate physical laws and interfere in quantum interactions, but they are never observable in the laboratory (i.e., in the classical limits, regarding the MWI). Thus, it appears that the main problem of the long-term ontology of the MWI is, in principle, its endeavor to speak about the fiercely serious philosophical topic of "classical reality" without constructing a firm experimental foundation.²⁰

One of the most fundamental issues with the classical explanations of the MWI arises from the substitution of the probability of an event's occurrence with its certainty of existence. This leads to the guaranteed creation of semi-deterministic worlds in long-term processes, despite their extremely low probability of occurrence.²¹ The other flaw in classical explanations of the MWI is likely that the ontology of this interpretation imposes no limits on the existence of parallel worlds, leading to paradoxical facts within classical limits due to the vast number of components involved. This issue vividly recalls Russell's paradox [58], where he effectively demonstrated that borderless definitions

²⁰ See discussions in [1, 3, 8, 9, 12, 14, 20, 35, 42–44, 66].

²¹ Since they are practically coded by a Lebesgue null set of rational numbers, i.e., $\mathbb{Q} \cap [0, 1)$.

encounter serious contradictions within themselves; When the elements of a collection increase enormously there would be a lack of control over the consistency of their interrelations. Therefore, the borderless long-term ontology of the MWI must be seriously reconsidered and only a "small category" of parallel worlds has to be preserved for the interpretation in classical limits [47].

III. SUMMERY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, with proving two theorems it has been shown that the ontology of the MWI is mathematically contradictory at classical limits and semi-deterministic parallel worlds must be excluded from the long-term processes of the interpretation. To prove this, we first showed in **Theorem 1** that the final assessment function f , which determines the rate of validity of the uncertainty of quantum mechanics, must be a continuous function on the space of created parallel worlds. This means that f can properly reflect the topological structure of the long-term ontology of the MWI. Then, we proved in **Theorem 2** that in the long-term ontology of the MWI, f must have significant variations in small distances, which is practically impossible. Hence, since the existence of the indeterministic parallel worlds aligns with the nature of quantum mechanics, we conclude that the semi-deterministic worlds must become extinct in the MWI along time.

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